

Protocol Template for Investigator-Initiated Studies

Template Instructions

Sections will expand to fit your responses.

Keep an electronic copy to modify when making changes either as directed by the IRB, or for amendments/modifications.

Mark sections NA if they are not applicable to your research.

Please use lay language, avoid professional jargon and define all abbreviations when they first appear.

PROTOCOL TITLE:

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Response: Risk Factors Associated with Adverse Events in Patients with Non-ruptured Thoracic Aortic Aneurysm: A Review From The New York State SPARCS Database

PROTOCOL VERSION/AMENDMENT # AND DATE

Response: *Version 1 (November 30, 2021)*

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR:

Response: *Dr. Laurie Shroyer*

DATE:

Response: *11/30/2021*

1.0 Objectives

1.1 Describe the purpose, specific aims, or objectives of this research. Specifically, explain why it is important to do the study.

Response: Thoracic aortic aneurysms (TAA) are usually a silent disease that can prove fatal if complications (i.e., rupture or dissection) arise. Aortic diameter has been described as a major risk factor for TAA adverse outcome or surgical intervention. Other comorbidities and importantly socioeconomic factors are less well analyzed variables in large population studies. Using the New York State (NYS) Statewide Planning and Research Cooperative Systems (SPARCS) database, the purpose of this retrospective cohort study is to identify the risk factors associated with adverse outcomes in a patient population with newly diagnosed non-ruptured TAA between the time range of 2005-2018.

1.2 State the hypothesis to be tested, if applicable.

NOTE: A hypothesis is a specific, testable prediction about what you expect to happen in your study that corresponds with your above listed objectives.

Response:

H(0): There will be no risk factors in thoracic aortic aneurysm diagnosis, propensity-adjusted treatment, and risk-adjusted outcome rates for New York State between the time range 2005-2018.

Additionally, the following hypotheses will be tested:

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(0): There will be no trends over time in the TAA risk-adjusted outcomes for New York State between the time range 2005-2018.

H(0): There will be no trends over time in outcome rates when comparing ruptured versus non-ruptured TAA patients for New York State between the time range 2005-2018.

H(0): There will be no trends over time in the overall TAA population propensity adjusted treatment rates for New York State between the time range 2005-2018.

H(0): There will be no trends over time, when comparing the ruptured versus non-ruptured TAA patients, in propensity adjusted treatment rates for New York State between the time range 2005-2018.

Additionally, other sub-analyses may be required to explore the primary associations found in more depth. Thus, secondary and tertiary analyses may be conducted.

2.0 Scientific/Safety Endpoints

2.1 Describe the scientific endpoint(s), the main result or occurrence under study.

NOTE: Scientific endpoints are outcomes defined before the study begins to determine whether the objectives of the study have been met and to draw conclusions from the data. Include primary and secondary endpoints. Some example endpoints are: reduction of symptoms, improvement in quality of life, or survival. Your response should not be a date.

Response: 2-year BTH rate, 2 year death rate, Time to 2 year death, Time to 2 year surgery, 30 day readmission, 2-year urgent/emergent and elective intervention rates, and 30 day operative death

3.0 Background

3.1 Provide the scientific or scholarly background, rationale, and significance of the research based on the existing literature and how it will contribute/fill in gaps to existing knowledge.

Response: Complications of thoracic aortic aneurysms (TAA) are usually fatal. This potentially lethal disease is generally silent and indolent, most often discovered incidentally when reviewing images obtained for other clinical indications. The true TAA incidence is unknown as many patients are asymptomatic and until urgent/emergent symptoms arise. A 1994 Mayo Clinic study estimated that 10.4 persons out of 100,000 will have a TAA. Given the advent of increased imaging such as CT screening of smokers for lung cancer as well as the increased use of CT angiography for transcatheter aortic valve replacements (TAVR), the diagnosis of asymptomatic

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TAA is rising. Hence this 1994 estimate is likely too low, dramatically underestimating the current incidence of the disease.

Recent studies have shown evidence to support the increasing diagnosis of these asymptomatic TAA's. A recent England-Wales study determined the total TAA admission to increase over 2-fold from 4.4/100,000 in 1999 to 9.0/100,000 in 2010. Furthermore, a study in Sweden found that TAA admission rate increased for men from 10.7/100,000 to 16.7/100,000 and for women from 7.1/100,000 to 9.1/100,000 in the years from 1987-2002. Additionally, a more recent study identified decreasing US national trends of TAA rupture between the years 1999-2016. To-date, there are no US-based studies that provide reliable overall TAA incidence rates.

TAA complication rate is linked to increased aortic diameter, as well as familial and genetic contributors. Guidelines exist for procedural intervention when size criteria are met. But little is known about optimal management for patients with moderately enlarged TAA in terms of optimal surveillance or screening. To begin addressing this insufficiency, it is necessary to first understand the scope of the problem. We therefore propose, using the New York State SPARCS data set, to obtain hospital data that will help inform the incidence of this disease and risk factors involved.

3.2 *Include complete citations or references:*

Response:

1. Von Allmen, R. S., A. Anjum, and J. T. Powell. "Incidence of descending aortic pathology and evaluation of the impact of thoracic endovascular aortic repair: a population-based study in England and Wales from 1999 to 2010." *European Journal of Vascular and Endovascular Surgery* 45.2 (2013): 154-159.

2. LeMaire SA, Russell L. Epidemiology of thoracic aortic dissection. *Nat Rev Cardiol.* 2011;8(2):103-113.

3. Olsson C, Thelin S, Ståhle E, Ekblom A, Granath F. Thoracic aortic aneurysm and dissection: increasing prevalence and improved outcomes reported in a nationwide population-based study of more than 14,000 cases from 1987 to 2002. *Circulation.* 2006;114(24):2611-2618.

4. Prakash SK, Haden-Pinneri K, Milewicz DM. Susceptibility to acute thoracic aortic dissections in patients dying outside the hospital: an autopsy study. *Am Heart J.* 2011;162(3):474-479.

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5. Abdulameer H, Al Taii H, Al-Kindi SG, Milner R. Epidemiology of fatal ruptured aortic aneurysms in the United States (1999-2016). *J Vasc Surg*. 2019;69(2):378-384.e372.
6. Aberle DR, Adams AM, Berg CD, et al. Reduced lung-cancer mortality with low-dose computed tomographic screening. *N Engl J Med*. 2011;365(5):395-409.
7. Jacobs PC, Mali WP, Grobbee DE, van der Graaf Y. Prevalence of incidental findings in computed tomographic screening of the chest: a systematic review. *J Comput Assist Tomogr*. 2008;32(2):214-221.
8. Swensen SJ, Jett JR, Hartman TE, et al. CT screening for lung cancer: five-year prospective experience. *Radiology*. 2005;235(1):259-265.
9. Detterbeck FC, Mazzone PJ, Naidich DP, Bach PB. Screening for lung cancer: Diagnosis and management of lung cancer, 3rd ed: American College of Chest Physicians evidence-based clinical practice guidelines. *Chest*. 2013;143(5 Suppl):e78S-e92S.
10. Kontopantelis E, Doran T, Springate DA, Buchan I, Reeves D. Regression based quasi-experimental approach when randomisation is not an option: interrupted time series analysis. *Bmj*. 2015;350:h2750.
11. Lodewycks CL, Prior HJ, Hiebert BM, et al. A Province-Wide Analysis of the Epidemiology of Thoracic Aortic Disease: Incidence Is Increasing in a Sex-Specific Way. *Can J Cardiol*. 2020;36(11):1729-1738.
12. Saeyeldin AA, Velasquez CA, Mahmood SUB, et al. Thoracic aortic aneurysm: unlocking the "silent killer" secrets. *Gen Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 2019;67(1):1-11.

4.0 Study Design

4.1 Describe and explain the study design (e.g. case-control, cross-sectional, ethnographic, experimental, interventional, longitudinal, and observational). Indicate if there is randomization, blinding, control group, etc. If randomizing, explain how this will be achieved.

Response: This retrospective observational cohort study will be done using the SPARCS Health Facts dataset. With the help of the SBU SOM Bioinformatics Department and Biostatistics Core Lab, the SPARCS database will be matched/merged to the enclosed coding listings to create a study-specific de-identified TAA database. Furthermore, the Bioinformatics and Biostatistics team members will be responsible for providing the descriptive statistics listed below as well as providing a study-database for future analyses. For this study's primary hypothesis related to

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diagnosis, propensity-adjusted treatment, and risk-adjusted outcome rates, a p-value of <0.001 will be used (all p-values will be reported by separate interpretation by readers). All secondary and tertiary analyses, as well as all exploratory analyses, will use a p-value of < 0.01. SAS version 9.4 will be used to complete all the necessary statistical tests.

5.0 Local Number of Subjects

5.1 Indicate the total number of subjects who will be enrolled or records that will be reviewed through Stony Brook.

Response: The SPARCS database has approximately 200,000 records with a TAA diagnosis. This study will use the subset of records that contain ICD9/ICD10 diagnosis code for nonruptured, dissected, or ruptured TAA.

5.2 If this study is only being conducted through Stony Brook, provide statistical justification (i.e. power analysis) for the number of subjects provided in 5.1 above. If qualitative research, so state, and provide general justification for the total number of subjects proposed.

Response: The deidentified NYS SPARCS database will be used for this study over the time period 2005-2018. The population will include all patients with an initial diagnosis of non-ruptured TAA that have not had prior cardiac interventions. Based upon index admission, TAA patients will be classified into patient with index encounter intervention versus later intervention versus no intervention sub-groups. From 2005 to 2018, the SPARCS database has approximately 200,000 records with a TAA diagnosis. Given this very large database, sample size or power were not study-relevant considerations.

5.3 If applicable, indicate your screen failure rate, i.e., how many subjects you expect to screen to reach your target sample.

Response: NA.

5.4 Justify the feasibility of recruiting the proposed number of eligible subjects within the anticipated recruitment period. For example, how many potential subjects do you have access to? What percentage of those potential subjects do you need to recruit?

Response: NA.

6.0 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

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NOTE: If your study is more than minimal risk, you must also upload a copy of your inclusion/exclusion checklist (with space for specific subject values) to be completed at time of enrollment of each subject.

6.1 Describe, in bullet points, the criteria that define who will be included in this study:

Response: *Using the SPARCS database, records of patients above the age of 18 years old with a TAA nonruptured diagnosis.*

6.2 Describe, in bullet points, the criteria that define who will be excluded from this study:

Response: *Any records of patients under the age of 18 years old and/or without an identifiable TAA diagnosis.*

6.3 Describe how individuals will be screened for eligibility. Upload all relevant screening documents with your submission (screening protocol, script, questionnaire). Identify who will certify that subjects meet eligibility requirements.

Response: *NA.*

6.4 Indicate whether you are specifically recruiting or targeting any of the following special populations in your study using the checkboxes below. (You will be asked for additional information in Section 7 if you check any of these boxes)

Response: All records that exist in the SPARCS database will be eligible for study consideration. None of the following potentially vulnerable sub-populations are specifically being analyzed. However, patients under the age of 18 will not be included in this study.

- Adults unable to consent
- Minors (under 18 years old)
- Pregnant women
- Prisoners

6.5 Indicate if you will include minorities (American Indians, Alaskan Native, Asian, Native Hawaiian, Pacific Islander, Black [not of Hispanic origin] and Hispanic) as Federal mandates require that you include minorities unless you can justify their exclusion

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Yes

No, Justify:

6.6 *Indicate whether you will include non-English speaking individuals in your study. Provide justification if you will specifically exclude non-English speaking individuals. Review <http://research.stonybrook.edu/human-subjects-standard-operating-procedures/policy-non-english-speakers-research-subjects> for SBU policy on inclusion of non-English speakers. Upload any translated materials (consent, questionnaires, etc).*

Response: NA.

7.0 Vulnerable Populations

7.1 *For research that involves pregnant women, review, complete and upload Supplemental Form A: Pregnant Women, Fetuses, Non-Viable Neonates , or Neonates of Uncertain Viability.*

Confirmed

N/A: This research does not involve pregnant women.

7.2 *For research that involves neonates of uncertain viability or non-viable neonates, review, complete and upload Supplemental Form A: Pregnant Women, Fetuses, Non-Viable Neonates, or Neonates of Uncertain Viability.*

Confirmed

N/A: This research does not involve non-viable neonates or neonates of uncertain viability.

7.3 *For research that involves prisoners, review, complete and upload Supplemental Form H: Prisoners*

Confirmed

N/A: This research does not involve prisoners.

7.4 *For research that involves minors (under 18 years), review, complete and upload Supplemental Form F: Minors*

Confirmed

N/A: This research does not involve persons who have not attained the legal age for consent to treatments or procedures (“children”).

7.5 *For research that involves adults who cannot consent for themselves, you will be asked additional information in Section 25 (“Informed Consent”)*

PROTOCOL TITLE:

- Confirmed
- N/A: This research does not involve this population

7.6 Consider if other specifically targeted populations such as students, employees of a specific firm, or educationally or economically disadvantaged persons are vulnerable. Provide information regarding their safeguards and protections, including safeguards to eliminate coercion or undue influence.

Safeguards include:

- N/A

8.0 Eligibility Screening

8.1 Describe screening procedures for determining subjects' eligibility. Screening refers to determining if prospective participants meet inclusion and exclusion criteria.

 Include all relevant screening documents with your submission (e.g. screening protocol, script, questionnaires) as attachments.

Response:

- N/A: There is no screening as part of this protocol.

9.0 Recruitment Methods

N/A: This is a records review only, and subjects will not be recruited. NOTE: If you select this option, please make sure that all records review procedures and inclusion/exclusion screening are adequately described in other sections, including date range for records that will be reviewed.

9.1 Describe source of subjects: When, where, and how potential subjects will be recruited.

NOTE: Recruitment refers to how you are identifying potential participants and introducing them to the study. These may include, but are not limited to: ResearchMatch.org, physician referral, Office of Clinical Trials database, West Campus departmental pools, reviewing medical charts, Research Participant Groups/help groups, advertising companies, call centers, in person announcements / presentations

Response: The NYS SPARCS database will be used to obtain patient records. De-identified reports will be provided from this database.

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9.2 *Describe how you will protect the privacy interests of prospective subjects during the recruitment process.*

NOTE: Privacy refers to an individual's right to control access to him or herself. This is NOT asking about confidentiality of data.

Response: The SPARCS database will be maintained in the Stony Brook Hospital secured shared drive with oversight by Dr. McLarty (PI) and Dr. Shroyer (co-PI). The Stony Brook University Hospital's shared drive is HIPAA compliant with file folder-specific access authenticated. Drs. McLarty and Shroyer will have the Stony Brook Hospital Information Technology provide the rest of the participants in the project read-only access to select file folders, as well as the study's data sets will not resident on any other computers. Out of Hospital access for analytical team members will be provided through a virtual private network (VPN); VPN ensures the use and transfer of data set in an encrypted and confidential manner. Following analyses, summary reports will be provided to study participants by e-mail.

9.3 *Identify/describe any materials that will be used to screen/recruit subjects and upload copies of these documents with the application. They may include, but are not limited to Telephone scripts for calling, flyers, Questionnaires, Posters, Letters or written material to be sent or emailed, pamphlets, posted advertisements, email invitations.*

Response: NA/Records will be obtained from NYS SPARCS database.

10.0 Research Procedures

Provide a detailed description of all research procedures or activities being performed on the research subjects. **This should serve as a blueprint for your study and include enough detail so that another investigator could pick up your protocol and replicate the research.** For studies that have multiple or complex visits or procedures, consider the addition of a schedule of events table in in your response. Be sure to include:

- Procedures being performed to monitor subjects for safety or to minimize risks.
- All drugs and devices used in the research and the purpose of their use, and their regulatory status

Response: Please see the attached protocol

10.1 *Describe what data, including long-term follow-up, will be collected.*

NOTE: For studies with multiple data collection points or long-term follow up, consider the addition of a schedule or table in your response.

Response: SPARCS database records will be screened for patients above the age of 18 and diagnosed with non-ruptured TAA. Risk factors (e.g., hypertension, diabetes, aortic valve

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disease, dyslipidemia, etc) and treatment attempts (e.g., surgical repair, transcatheter endovascular aortic repair, hybrid intervention) will be documented.

¶ *List, and upload, any instruments or measurement tools used to collect data (e.g. survey, scripts, questionnaire, interview guide, validated instrument, data collection form).*

Response: Please review the protocol for attached sheets codes (e.g., diagnosis codes [ICD-9, ICD-10], and procedure codes [CPT]).

10.2 Describe any source records that will be used to collect data about subjects (e.g. school records, electronic medical records) and include the date range for records that will be accessed..

Response: NA. The SPARCS database represents the source of records for this study.

10.3 Indicate whether or not the results for individual subjects, such as results of investigational diagnostic tests, genetic tests, or incidental findings will be shared with subjects or others (e.g., the subject's primary care physician) and if so, describe how these will be shared.

Response: NA.

10.4 Indicate whether or not generalized study results will be shared with subjects or others, and if so, describe how these will be shared.

Response:

11.0 Study Timelines

11.1 Describe the anticipated duration of the study needed to enroll all study subjects.

Response: NA. The current study is recorded in the SPARCS database.

11.2 Describe the duration of an individual subject's participation in the study. Include length of study visits, and overall study follow-up time.

Response: NA. The current study is recorded in the SPARCS database.

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11.3 Describe the estimated duration for the investigators to complete this study (i.e. all data is collected and all analyses have been completed).

Response: NA. The current study is recorded in the SPARCS database.

12.0 Research Setting

12.1 Describe all facilities/sites/locations where you will be screening and conducting research procedures. Include a description of the security and privacy of the facilities (e.g. locked facility, limited access, privacy barriers). Facility, department, and type of room are relevant. Do not abbreviate facility names.

Example: "A classroom setting in the Department of Psychology equipped with a computer with relevant survey administration software," "The angiogram suite at Stony Brook University Hospital, a fully accredited tertiary care institution within New York State with badge access,"

Response: This study will be conducted at the SBU SOM. Given de-identified reports will be used, Dr. McLarty and Dr. Shroyer team members may utilize both office-based and personal (e.g., laptop) computers for the planned analyses.

12.2 For research procedures being conducted, for this study, external to SBU and its affiliates (e.g., in schools, out-of-state, internationally, etc.) describe:

- *Site-specific regulations or customs affecting the research*
- *The composition and involvement of any community advisory board*
- *Local scientific and ethical review structure outside the organization.*
- *Local issues affecting the research and rights of research subjects.*

NOTE: This question is not referring to multi-center research. If this research is being conducted internationally, Supplemental Form C must be completed and uploaded.

Response:

N/A: This study is not conducted outside of SBU or its affiliates.

13.0 Resources and Qualifications

13.1 The Principal Investigator (PI) must confirm, in consultation with Chair and Dean as applicable, that adequate resources are present to conduct and complete the study compliantly and safely. Specifically:

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- NO YES *The proposed subject population(s) are available in sufficient numbers to meet the study requirements*
- NO YES *Sufficient funds are available to conduct and complete the study compliantly and safely*
- NO YES *The PI and study team have sufficient time to conduct and complete the study compliantly and safely*
- NO YES *The PI has determined that the named study team is qualified to conduct the research compliantly and to monitor the safety and welfare of the enrolled research subjects effectively.*
- NO YES *The PI ensures that the study team is fully aware of his/her involvement in this study and the details of the study protocol*
- NO YES *The PI ensures that the study teams will only be involved in research procedures for which they have been trained, and are currently certified and/or licensed, if required..*

13.2 *Describe the availability of medical or psychological resources that subjects might need as a result of anticipated consequences of the human research, if applicable. (e.g, “on-call availability of a counselor or psychologist for a study that screens subjects for depression”).*

Response: NA.

13.3 *Describe your process to ensure that all study team members are updated on the progress of the research and the regulatory requirements (including enrolled subjects, unanticipated problems etc.)*

Response: Progress of the research study will be discussed and followed through weekly/biweekly meetings and conference calls. Preliminary reports and literature search will be shared and reported via email and phone.

14.0 Other Approvals

14. *List approvals that will be obtained prior to commencing the research (e.g., University Hospital sign-offs per the UH Application, Cancer Center Scientific review, school, external site, funding agency, laboratory, Radiation Safety, IBC, SCRO, IACUC, RDRC).*

Response:

- N/A: This study does not require any other approvals.

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15.0 Provisions to Protect the Privacy Interests of Subjects

15.1 Describe how you will protect subjects' privacy interests during the course of this research and any steps you will take to make the subject feel at ease.

NOTE: Privacy refers to an individual's desire/right to control access to or to place limits on whom they interact with or whom they provide personal information. Privacy applies to the person. Confidentiality refers to how data collected about individuals for the research will be protected by the researcher from release. Confidentiality applies to the data.

Examples of appropriate responses include: "participant only meets with a study coordinator in a private office setting where no one can overhear", or "the participant is reminded that they are free to refuse to answer any questions that they do not feel comfortable answering."

Response: NA.

16.0 Data Management and Analysis

16.1 Describe the data analysis plan, including any statistical procedures. This section applies to both quantitative and qualitative analysis.

Response: Bioinformatics team will be responsible for providing the descriptive statistics listed above as well as providing a study-database for future analyses. For this study's primary hypothesis related to trends over time in diagnosis, treatment, and outcome rates, a p-value of 0.05 will be used. All secondary and tertiary analyses, as well as all exploratory analyses, will use a p-value of < 0.01. SAS version 9.4 will be used to complete all the necessary statistical tests.

16.2 If applicable, provide a power analysis.

NOTE: This may not apply to certain types of studies, including chart/records reviews, survey studies, or observational studies. This question is asked to elicit whether the investigator has an adequate sample size to achieve the study objectives and justify a conclusion.

Response: NA.

17.0 Confidentiality

A. Confidentiality/Security of Study Data

Describe the local procedures for maintenance of security and confidentiality of **study data and any records that will be reviewed for data collection.**

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17.1 Where and how will all data and records be stored? Include information about: password protection, encryption, physical controls, authorization of access, certificates of confidentiality, and separation of identifiers and data, as applicable. Include physical (e.g. paper) and electronic files.

Response: NA.

17.2 How long will the data be stored?

Response: NA.

17.3 Who will have access to the data?

Response: Drs. McLarty and Shroyer study's team members (includes, but not limited to):
Co-Investigator: Dr. Thomas Bilfinger, Dr. Henry Tannous, Dr. Jie Yang
Trainees: Joshua Helali, Mohammad Noubani, Annet Kuruvilla, Jahnvi Bansal, Ashutosh Yaligar
Biostatistician: Junying Wang

17.4 Who is responsible for receipt or transmission of the data?

Response: Dr. McLarty and Dr. Shroyer

17.5 How will the data be transported/transmitted?

Response: The data will be transmitted to Dr. McLarty and Dr. Shroyer via an e-mail link to a protected TAA shared drive. Dr. Shroyer will be responsible for downloading the study data.

B. Confidentiality of Study Specimens

Describe the local procedures for maintenance of confidentiality of study specimens.

N/A: No specimens will be collected or analyzed in this research.
(Skip to Section 18.0)

17.6 Where and how will all specimens be stored? Include information about: physical controls, authorization of access, and labeling of specimens, as applicable.

Response:

17.7 How long will the specimens be stored?

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Response:

17.8 Who will have access to the specimens?

Response:

17.9 Who is responsible for receipt or transmission of the specimens?

Response:

17.10 How will the specimens be transported?

Response:

18.0 Provisions to Monitor the Data to Ensure the Safety of Subjects

N/A: This study is not enrolling subjects OR is limited to records review procedures only OR is a minimal risk study

18.1 Describe the plan to evaluate the data periodically regarding both harms and benefits to determine whether subjects remain safe. The plan might include establishing a data safety monitoring committee and a plan for reporting data monitoring committee findings to the IRB and the sponsor.

Response:

18.2 Describe what data are reviewed, including safety data, untoward events, and efficacy data.

Response:

18.3 Describe any primary or secondary safety endpoints.

Response:

18.4 Describe how the safety information will be collected (e.g., with case report forms, at study visits, by telephone calls with participants).

Response:

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18.5 Describe the frequency of safety data collection, including when safety data collection starts.

Response:

18.6 Describe who will review the safety data.

Response:

18.7 Describe the frequency or periodicity of review of cumulative safety data.

Response:

18.8 Describe the statistical tests for analyzing the safety data to determine whether harm is occurring.

Response:

18.9 Describe any conditions that trigger an immediate suspension of the research.

Response:

19.0 Withdrawal of Subjects

N/A: This study is not enrolling subjects. This section does not apply.

19.1 Describe anticipated circumstances under which subjects may be withdrawn from the research without their consent.

Response:

19.2 Describe any procedures for orderly termination.

NOTE: Examples may include return of study drug, exit interview with clinician.

Include whether additional follow up is recommended for safety reasons for physical or emotional health.

Response:

19.3 Describe procedures that will be followed when subjects withdraw from the research, including retention of already collected data, and partial withdrawal from procedures with continued data collection, as applicable.

Response:

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19.4 Describe what will happen to data already collected.

Response:

20.0 Risks to Subjects

20.1 In your opinion, what is the overall risk (physical and nonphysical) to research subjects in this study (minimal, greater than minimal or unknown)

Response: Given deidentified data are being used for this study, it does not appear to meet the definition of "human subjects" research. Thus, an exemption is requested.

20.2 Describe if any subjects are withdrawn from therapeutic procedures or drugs (e.g., washout periods) prior to, or during, their participation in the study.

Response: NA. This study should be classified as "not human subjects" research.

20.3 List the reasonably foreseeable risks, discomforts, hazards, or inconveniences to the subjects related to their participation in the research. Consider physical, psychological, social, legal, and economic risks. Include a description of the probability, magnitude, duration, and reversibility of the risks.

NOTE: Breach of confidentiality is always a risk for identifiable subject data.

Response: NA.

20.4 Describe procedures performed to minimize the probability or magnitude of risks, including procedures being performed to monitor subjects for safety.

Response: NA.

20.5 If applicable, indicate which procedures may have risks to the subjects that are currently unforeseeable.

Response: NA.

20.6 Indicate which research procedures, if any, may have risks to an embryo or fetus should the subject be or become pregnant.

Response: N/A

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N/A

20.7 If you responded to 20.6 that there are such risks, how will you minimize the risk of a pregnancy occurring during the course of the study? (Select all that apply)

- Counseling on birth control and /or abstinence
- Pregnancy test during the study
- Pregnancy test prior to initiation of the study
- Other _____
- N/A

20.8 If applicable, describe possible risks to others who are not subjects.

Response: This is a study that includes patient records that will be obtained from the NYS SPARCS database. Therefore, it poses no risk to patients whatsoever

21.0 Potential Benefits to Subjects

21.1 Describe the potential benefits that individual subjects may experience by taking part in the research. Include the probability, magnitude, and duration of the potential benefits.

Response: NA

21.2 Indicate if there is no direct benefit.

NOTE: Compensation cannot be stated as a benefit.

Response: NA

Indicate if there is a potential benefit to others, future science or society.

Response: This study will, for the first time, identify the true incidence rate of thoracic aortic aneurysm and its risk factors associated with adverse events among the NYS population. This study may represent the first leap towards the plan of monitoring and management of thoracic aortic aneurysms.

22.0 Compensation for Research-Related Injury

N/A: The research procedures for this study do not present risk of research related injury. This section does not apply.

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22.1 If the research procedures carry a risk of research related injury, describe the available compensation to subjects in the event that such injury should occur.

Response:

22.2 Provide a copy of contract language, if any, relevant to compensation for research related injury.

NOTE: If the contract is not yet approved at the time of this submission, submit the current version here. If the contract is later approved with different language regarding research related injury, you must modify your response here and submit an amendment to the IRB for review and approval.

Response: NA

23.0 Economic Burden to Subjects

23.1 Describe any costs that subjects may be responsible for because of participation in the research.

NOTE: Some examples include transportation or parking.

Response:

N/A: This study is not enrolling subjects, or is limited to records review procedures only. This section does not apply.

24.0 Compensation for Participation

N/A: There is no compensation for participation. This section does not apply.

24.1 Describe the amount/nature and timing/scheduling of any compensation to subjects, including monetary, course credit, or gift card compensation. Describe any prorated payments based on participation.

Response: NA

24.2 Justify the amount and scheduling of payments described above to ensure that they are reasonable and commensurate with the expected contributions of the participant. If multiple visits are involved payments should be prorated.

Note: If using West Campus Departmental pools, participation in studies may be offered for credit in class but students MUST be given other options for fulfilling the research component that are comparable in terms of time, effort, and education benefit. Please list alternative activities

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Response: NA

25.0 Informed Consent

25.1 *Will you be obtaining consent from subjects?*

Yes *(If yes, Provide responses to each question in this Section, and upload your consent documents where indicated in the electronic submission system)*

No *(If no, Skip to next section)*

25.2 *Describe how the capacity to consent will be assessed for all subjects. Review for guidance <http://research.stonybrook.edu/human-subjects-standard-operating-procedures/determining-potential-adult-subjects-ability-consent>:*

Response:

25.3 *Describe the consent process that will be conducted to ensure that subject is fully informed regarding study details and subject rights. Include where the consent process will take place, with consideration of the need to protect the subject's right to privacy.*

Response:

25.4 *Describe how you will ensure that subjects are provided with sufficient time to consider taking part in the research study. Detail if there is there any time period expected between informing the prospective subject and obtaining the consent.*

NOTE: It is respectful to the prospective subject to ensure that sufficient time is given to have their questions answered and to consider their participation

Response:

25.5 *Describe the process to ensure ongoing consent, defined as a subject's willingness to continue participation for the duration of the research study.*

Response:

Non-English Speaking Subjects

N/A: This study will not enroll Non-English speaking subjects.

25.6 *Indicate which language(s) other than English are likely to be spoken/understood by your prospective study population or their legally authorized representatives.*

PROTOCOL TITLE:

Response:

25.7 If subjects who do not speak English will be enrolled, describe the process to consent the subjects, as well as the process to be used to ensure their understanding of research procedures throughout the conduct of the study. Review SOP's section 17.8 for important policies in this regard: <http://research.stonybrook.edu/human-subjects-standard-operating-procedures/policy-non-english-speakers-research-subjects-for-SBU-policy-on-inclusion-of-non-English-speakers>.

Response:

Adults Unable to Consent

N/A: This study will not enroll adults unable to consent.

25.8 Justify why it is necessary to include adult subjects who are unable to consent.

Response: The records used for the study are extracted from NYS SPARCS database and requires no consents from adults.

25.9 Describe how you will identify Legally Authorized Representatives (LAR) for the subjects that will be consistent with the NYS Family Health Care Decisions Act (FHCDA; see <http://research.stonybrook.edu/human-subjects-standard-operating-procedures/definitions-2>). Indicate why it is necessary to include subjects who are unable to consent.

Note: For research conducted outside of New York State, provide information that describes which individuals are authorized under applicable law to consent on behalf of a prospective subject to their participation in the research.

Response: NA

25.10 Describe the process for obtaining assent from the adult subjects. Indicate whether assent will be obtained from all, some, or none of the subjects. If some, indicate which adults will be required to assent and which will not.

Response: NA

If assent will not be obtained from some or all subjects, provide an explanation of why not.

Response: The records used for the study are extracted from the NYS SPARCS database and pose no risk whatsoever to patients. Therefore, there is no consent required from adult patients.

PROTOCOL TITLE:

25.11 Describe whether assent of the adult subjects will be documented and the process to document assent.

Response: NA

25.12 Describe how you will obtain consent from a subject to use their data if they later become capable of consent. How will competence be assessed and by whom?

Response: NA

26.0 Waiver or Alteration of Consent Process

Complete this section if:

- Informed consent will not be obtained at all
 - Informed consent will be obtained, but not documented, or
 - consent will be obtained, but not all required information will be disclosed (e.g., in deception research)
- N/A:** A waiver or alteration of consent is not being requested.

26.1 Review, complete, and upload SUPPLEMENTAL FORM G: Consent Waivers

Confirmed

26.2 If the research involves a waiver of the consent process for planned emergency research, please contact the Office of Research Compliance for guidance regarding assistance in complying with federal regulations governing this activity (see: <https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfcfr/CFRSearch.cfm?fr=50.24>)

27.0 Multi-Site Research (Multisite/Multicenter Only)

N/A: This study is not an investigator-initiated, multi-site study. This section does not apply.

27.1 If this is a multi-site study where SBU is the lead site and/or the IRB of record, describe the processes to ensure communication among sites. Include:

- *All sites have the most current version of the IRB documents, including the protocol, consent document, and HIPAA authorization.*
- *All required approvals have been obtained at each site (including approval by the site's IRB of record).*
- *All modifications have been communicated to sites, and approved (including approval by the site's IRB of record) before the modification is implemented.*

PROTOCOL TITLE:

- *All engaged participating sites will safeguard data as required by local information security policies.*
- *All local site investigators conduct the study appropriately.*
- *All non-compliance with the study protocol or applicable requirements will be reported in accordance with local policy.*

Response: NA

27.2 *Describe the method for communicating to engaged participating sites:*

- *Problems*
- *Interim results*
- *Study closure*

Response: NA

27.3 *Indicate and statistically justify the total number of subjects that will be enrolled or records that will be reviewed **across all sites**.*

Response: NA

28.0 Banking Data or Specimens for Future Unspecified Use

N/A: This study is not storing data or specimens for research outside the scope of the present protocol. This section does not apply.

IMPORTANT: If you are proposing to bank specimens for future use, you may be subject to licensure requirements under the NYS Department of Health, and must be covered under the SBU license. See SOPs at <http://research.stonybrook.edu/human-subjects-standard-operating-procedures/data-tissue-registries-banks>

28.1 *If data will be banked for research outside of the scope of the present protocol, describe where the data will be stored, how long they will be stored, how will they be accessed, and who will have access to the data*

NOTE: Your response here must be consistent with the information provided to subjects in your Consent Documents

Response: NA

28.2 *If specimens will be banked (stored) for research outside of the scope of the present protocol, describe where the specimens will be stored, how long they will be*

PROTOCOL TITLE:

stored, identifiers that will be associated with each specimen, how will they be accessed, and who will have access to the specimens

NOTE: Your response here must be consistent with the information provided to subjects in your

Consent Documents

Response: NA

28.3 Describe the procedures to release banked data and/or specimens for future uses, including: the process to request a release, approvals required for release, who can obtain data or specimens, and the data to be provided with specimens.

Response: NA

29.0 Drugs and Devices

N/A: This study does not involve drugs or devices. This section does not apply.

29.1 Does this study involve use of radiopharmaceuticals? Yes No

29.2 For investigational devices (including marketed devices being used off label), Provide the following information below:

Where will the device(s) be stored? Note that the storage area must be within an area under the PI's control

Describe the security of the storage unit/facility

Provide full detail regarding how the dispensing of the device(s) will be controlled (accountability of removal/return of used devices, and disposition of remaining devices at the conclusion of the investigation) and documented (accounting records/logs)

Response: NA

29.3 For investigational drugs (including marketed drugs being used off label), will the services of the Investigational Drug Pharmacy be used for storage, dispensing, accounting the drug (required for research conducted at UH, HSC, Cancer Center, and Ambulatory Surgery Center)?

Yes

No →PI Provide the following information below:

- *Where will the drugs/biologics be stored? Note that the storage area must be within an area under the PI's control*
- *Describe the security of the storage unit/facility:*

PROTOCOL TITLE:

- *Provide full detail regarding dispensing of the drugs(s), how labeled, controlled (accountability, disposition of unused drug at the conclusion of the investigation) and documented (accounting records/logs):*

Response: NA

30.0 Sharing of Results with Subjects

30.1 Describe whether results (study results or individual subject results, such as results of investigational diagnostic tests, genetic tests, or incidental findings) will be shared with subjects or others (e.g., the subject's primary care physicians) and if so, describe how it will be shared.

Response: Targeted for a future submission to a cardiology or surgery journal (i.e., Circulation or The Journal of the American Medical Association Surgery), this research project is intended to result in an original peer-reviewed research article. These findings might be presented at national and/or international conferences as well pending journal's embargo.